

Human impact in complex classification of steel coils

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Abstract. This work explores different artificial intelligence based alternatives to create automatic classification system based on salience maps of coil surface when heavy unbalanced datasets are considered and where the labels have been assigned by human operators, considering different complex rules. After testing the possibilities of classifier setup process, additional effort was spend create synthetic features based on the characteristics of the salience maps and such features have been used to verify the need for additional check of scores coming from the human operators. Although it is a preliminary result, it provide evidences of the significant impact that confusing scores can have on the classifier final performance.

Keywords: surface defects; steel coils; salience maps; Artificial intelligence; Human effect on sample labeling

1 Introduction

Industry 4.0 has gained a significant amount of traction since becoming known. Smart and connected technologies are being embedded in organizations, assets and even people in the case of wearable devices, taking advantage of emerging capabilities from artificial intelligence (AI) to quantum computing (QC), to foster classical manufacturing and additive manufacturing processes with the help of the Internet of Things(IoT) [5, 13, 14].

There is a constant growth in the area of Artificial Intelligence driven by new available modeling techniques, platforms and solutions. That ecosystem quickly evolves toward better algorithms and wider practical applications in Industry. Although certification of these tools is a must to be achieved, its progressive implementation is making the costs to decrease.

AI has several advantages for the manufacturing industry when applied with the right approach. Some of the most relevant advantages for the manufacturing sector today:

- **Error reduction.**- After being trained, intelligent algorithms can perform very well tasks that are susceptible to errors in processes executed by humans, such as data-driven technical quality assessment [4]. Since algorithms are not susceptible to external factors, they should be unlikely to suffer these factors’ consequences.
- **Cost reduction.**- More attention to the asset management, integrating production scheduling with maintenance and operation tracking will provide a significant increase of overall equipment effectiveness (OEE) optimization [1].
- **Revenue Growth.**- With fewer errors and employees focused on more critical processes, decision-makers will have more time to think about the core business and leave other AI tasks [2].

Although there are many articles reporting successful AI application to manufacturing industry [7], much less contributions have shown the potentially disturbing effects in limited datasets that noncalibrated human decisions can have in the overall performance of AI models. This is the main goal that this paper wants to analyze. First, in Section 2 a use case related to the quality classification of flat steel products having difficulties in interpretation will be introduced. Section 3 explores the effectiveness of different AI based models and then Section 4 discusses the influence that operator’s decision being used in the labeling process means. Finally, conclusions and future research lines are presented in Section 5.

2 Use Case for analysis

The selected use case is related to a downstream flat steel production process, where a continuous annealing with zinc coated is produced (Hot Dip Galvanizing process). The quality process aims to identify surface defects by using a specialized computer vision system [9, 10, 3].

Single defects, usually from 5 cm – 50 cm (or rare up to 2 meter), depending on their severity and (if no rework is allowed) reason for blocking and downgrading. The following defect is classified into subgroups, considering the position on the strip and the appearance of the defect. Surface defects may have different origins. Starting from the caster and hot strip mill, the origin of slivers is continued, followed by the scale from the hot strip mill. The root causes of zinc pimples are various and can be found in HSM, Cold Roll mill and also in the Galva process itself. Zinc dross is a defect caused by dross from the zinc Pott in the Galva process. Even if all of those defects may have different origins and dimensions, the defect severity increases or pops up with the Galva process. The outcome of the visual inspection system with controlled illumination is processed to decide about the acceptability of the coils.

For storing the images and because of the coil size a tiling process is implemented in such a way that all the surface is resampled into 128*256 chunks and the defects found in each tile are cumulated. Fig. 1 shows examples of the different classes.

(a) Example of OK status (b) Example of NoK status (c) Human accepted coil

Fig. 1: Digital representation of coils with the adopted resolution

The goal is to create an AI based model able to interpret the complex rules being applied by the human operator to decide whether the existing defects are acceptable or not. To learn such complex rules a data-driven strategy was adopted, and to this end a dataset was created to learn from experience (by reviewing a significant set of classification images already assessed by human operators, for the same defect type) is a consistent alternative approach. In this case, the dataset covers 4649 images, where 4405 are OK and 244 are not OK.

```

num_classes=2
inChannel = 1
x, y = 128, 256
input_img = Input(shape = (x, y, inChannel))
def classifier(input_img):
    conv1 = Conv2D(8, (3, 3), activation='relu', padding='same')(input_img) #128 x 256 x 32
    b1 = BatchNormalization()(conv1)
    pool1 = MaxPooling2D(pool_size=(2, 2))(b1) #64 x 128 x 32
    conv2 = Conv2D(16, (3, 3), activation='relu', padding='same')(pool1) #64 x 128 x 48
    b2 = BatchNormalization()(conv2)
    pool2 = MaxPooling2D(pool_size=(2, 2))(b2) #32 x 64 x 48
    conv3 = Conv2D(32, (3, 3), activation='relu', padding='same')(pool2) #32 x 64 x 64
    b3 = BatchNormalization()(conv3)
    pool3 = MaxPooling2D(pool_size=(2, 2))(b3) #16 x 32 x 64
    conv4 = Conv2D(64, (3, 3), activation='relu', padding='same')(pool3) #32 x 64 x 64
    b4 = BatchNormalization()(conv4)
    pool4 = MaxPooling2D(pool_size=(2, 2))(b4) #16 x 32 x 64
    flat = Flatten()(pool4)
    den = Dense(256, activation='relu')(flat)
    den2 = Dense(32, activation='relu')(den)
    out = Dense(2, activation='softmax')(den2)
    return out

```

Fig. 2: Base architecture adopted as a reference

A significant constraint to be handled is the heavily imbalanced datasets (4405 vs 244) which can affect the learning process, as the initial sample distribution makes one class much more probable than the other one. Different deep learning techniques have been tested, including Convolutional Neural Networks (CNNs), but also in which different predefined configurations have been used to extract relevant feature sets, such as VGG16. Other alternatives, such as encoders and dimension compressors, that enable classifiers to be used in much lower dimensions were also tested.

Actually, the existing rule-based classifier is able to identify 643 as OK and 200 as NoK. For all the remaining 3806 coils, the automatic classification system

was not able to decide, and they have been sent to human operators for a final decision. Of them, 3762 have been labeled as OK by the human deciders, and 44 have been discarded. An example of the coils that are accepted is presented in Fig. 1c, where the input is the set of image pixels and the output is the binary classification. This model requires 2.1 million parameters.

Fig. 3: Different activation functions tested.

3 AI models in Quality Control

To establish a base case, to compare against, a classical CNN was used, with an architecture such as presented at Fig. 2.

An equal-size training set from the classes was created with 300 images in total, randomly selected. The results show the limited success found, mainly due to the limited size of the training set, and the interest in identifying the NotOK coils:

- Success ratio in class OK 40%.
- Success ratio in class NotOK 67%.

Different activation functions were tested to assess relevance without specific impact (see Fig. 3). As is well known from the different applications carried out for CNNs, overfitting occurs after a few epochs, which prevents many epochs from being used [8].

To try to determine the right strategy fighting against the imbalanced classes, currently there is a wide variety of solutions for this problem, although they can be grouped into:

- Adjustment of model parameters to penalize failures to detect minority class during training.
- Modify the data set to balance the classes. Within this group, it is possible to distinguish between oversampling techniques, which consist of increasing the number of samples of the minority class, and subsampling, which consist of reducing the number of samples of the majority class.

For the case under study, the first solution did not significantly improve the results, so the second group of solutions will be studied in more depth. SMOTE

technology [6] was implemented by studying both oversampling and undersampling to create a balanced training data set. Starting with oversampling, the dataset is separated into train, validation, and test:

- **Train:** is the set of images with which the model is trained, following the procedure discussed in the theoretical foundation. It consists of 3009 images of steel coils from the category defined as inspector_OK (insp_OK), and 170 images from the NoK category. After applying SMOTE, the training set is made up of 6018 images in total, half inspector_OK and half NoK.
- **Validation:** allows for evaluating the predictive capacity of the model before moving on to the test stage, as well as detect overfitting. In this case, it is made up of 37 images from the inspector_OK category and 37 from the NoK category.
- **Test:** It is used to evaluate the already trained models. In this case, three test sets will be used to study how the model behaves for each of the three categories. The first will be made up of the 643 images cataloged as OK, the second will be made up of the remaining 716 images of the inspector_OK category, and the third the remaining 37 images of the NoK class.

Table 1 shows the results obtained when training and testing the different CNN models tested, where three different sequences for the number of features in the convolution layers and three different sizes were used in the flatten layer. Indeed, different sizes of kernel for convolution were tested, and different sizes of maxpooling window was implemented. The last three architectures were extending the number of cascade blocks of con2d+batchnorm+maxpooling used, that produced more complex features. It should be noted that each of the models has been trained and tested ten times and the mean and standard deviation of the results have been calculated, to be able to compare in a consistent way.

The numerical values in green represented in Table 1 the mean percentage of correctly classified coils, while the values in yellow are the standard deviations, and allow us to estimate the dispersion or variability between the ten runs carried out for each model. In principle, to choose the best model, priority has been given to the detection of NOK coils, for security reasons, considering the importance of minimizing the value of the standard deviation. For this reason, among the first six models, CNN3 was chosen as the basis for continuing the experiments. However, increasing the size of the kernel of the convolution layers improved the NOK plate detection ability from 51.89% to 57.57%, in addition to decreasing the standard deviation of the results. Therefore, among the first nine models, CNN7 was chosen as the basis for further experimentation. In the third stage of testing, the architecture of the models was modified, and it was shown that in this case, reducing the number of layers improves the results. The CNN10 model is considered to have the best performance, as it correctly detects more than 60% of the NOK coils and reduces the standard deviation of its results somewhat more. Therefore, this will be taken as a reference to compare with the rest of the machine learning models.

The other approach, the subsampling [6], was also explored, in view of the results obtained so far. The same experiments as in the previous approach (CNNx)

Table 1: CNN over Data-set treated with Smote. Training and Validation accuracy depending on Epochs.

MODELS	AVERAGE(% SUCCESS)		STANDARD DEVIATION			
	<i>OK</i>	<i>Insp.OK</i>	<i>NoK</i>	<i>OK</i>	<i>Insp.OK</i>	<i>NoK</i>
CNN1	71.12	70.41	47.57	16.66	19.06	24.33
CNN2	78.96	78.30	42.97	9.72	10.10	14.87
CNN3	73.17	73.13	51.89	20.96	21.58	22.35
CNN4	75.27	76.45	40.54	17.34	16.98	22.74
CNN5	75.77	75.81	43.24	21.63	21.99	25.55
CNN6	76.58	75.17	50.51	18.57	20.78	27.61
CNN7	66.70	66.26	57.57	18.69	16.36	17.18
CNN8	71.15	70.60	52.43	16.55	15.69	20.41
CNN9	83.11	81.79	37.03	9.83	11.20	20.51
CNN10	68.79	64.53	60.54	14.66	17.72	17.06
CNN11	79.30	76.87	47.03	16.51	18.52	20.59
CNN12	68.27	68.42	55.68	20.58	21.89	24.86
CNN13	81.99	82.07	38.65	18.13	16.58	19.75

were carried out, but using subsampling to solve the class imbalance problem and balance the training set. The random undersampling method allows random undersampling of the majority class until the classes are balanced. With this proposal, in addition to solving the problem of data imbalance, the computational load is reduced, and therefore the training time. However, it also has certain drawbacks since for the models to generalize correctly, it is usually necessary to use a large amount of data, and with this technique useful images can be eliminated, which could worsen the results. This time the total set of images has been divided into:

- **Train:** 150 images from the inspector_OK category and 150 NoK images.
- **Validation:** 47 images from the inspector_OK category and 47 NoK images.
- **Test:** again, we have chosen to define three test sets to study how the model behaves with each of the classes. The first one is formed by the 643 OK images, the second by 3565 inspector_OK images, and the third by 47 NoK images.

Table 2 shows the results obtained by the different models for each of the categories defined in the dataset. At first glance, we see that all the models work better than those studied previously, so for this application, the subsampling technique works better than SMOTE and oversampling. In this case, among the first six models, CNN2 was chosen as the best, with a precision of 73.19% in the detection of NoK coils and a very low standard deviation value, indicating low variability in results. Starting from the latter as the reference model and continuing with the experiments to compare with the rest of the machine learning models.

Another technique used was the autoencoders, where the goal was to compress the input to a reduced space that contains its main characteristics, and a

Table 2: CNN over Data-set treated with Undersampling Smote. Training and Validation accuracy depending on Epochs.

MODELS	AVERAGE(% SUCCESS)			STANDARD DEVIATION		
	<i>OK</i>	<i>Insp.OK</i>	<i>NoK</i>	<i>OK</i>	<i>Insp.OK</i>	<i>NoK</i>
CNN1	69.88	66.51	71.70	9.05	10.08	9.13
CNN2	69.21	66.65	73.19	8.62	7.67	4.87
CNN3	73.11	70.11	70.43	6.10	7.72	7.74
CNN4	68.62	66.68	69.36	5.77	5.98	6.94
CNN5	71.70	69.46	68.72	11.05	10.66	11.10
CNN6	74.65	72.81	65.74	8.42	9.29	10.53
CNN7	68.91	64.40	72.34	10.19	11.69	12.94
CNN8	73.92	70.59	67.23	7.12	7.95	11.97
CNN9	68.71	66.49	74.04	9.88	9.85	9.51
CNN10	67.40	66.86	69.57	12.18	11.25	9.57
CNN11	73.33	71.24	70.43	6.72	7.38	5.82
CNN12	71.70	69.50	65.74	10.42	9.75	10.09
CNN13	65.65	61.71	68.09	13.42	15.10	23.62

decoder, whose job is to reconstruct the original input starting from said compressed information. The idea is to study whether this can be used to improve the results obtained by conventional convolutional classifiers. The strategy to follow in this case has been to design several auto-encoders to see which of them best reconstructed the input images. After choosing it and assuming that its reduced space was therefore the one that best represented the initial image, the idea is to take advantage of the encoder part as a feature extractor and add the relevant layers to build an algorithm capable of classifying coils correctly. First, the reconstruction capacity of six auto-encoders with different architectures was studied. To do this, two different patterns are defined that will facilitate the subsequent description of the autoencoders. Once these patterns have been defined, the architecture of the autoencoders can be described from them (in all the cases the encoder and decoder were symmetric) describing the encoder (two, three, and four type 1, and the same for the type 2 pattern).

The number of feature maps of the convolution layers, as well as other parameters, has been chosen considering the results obtained in tests with conventional convolutional classifiers. And by its training, the learned lesson can be formulated as: *The greater the number of layers, the blurrier, and the more convolutions, the better the reconstruction.*

Another technique under exploratory analysis was the extraction of engineering features based on the pre-trained VGG model [11] to identify objects on Imagenet (more than 14 million images from more than 1000 different classes), where the only transformation was to accommodate the input images in the VGG model (224x224x3). A transfer learning strategy with eleven different configurations was tested, producing the results presented in Table 3, where a different number of layers were defined as nontrainable, and a different number of neurons was adopted in dense layers.

Table 3: Results obtained from the VGG based classifiers.

MODELS	AVERAGE(% SUCCESS)			STANDARD DEVIATION		
	<i>OK</i>	<i>Insp.OK</i>	<i>NoK</i>	<i>OK</i>	<i>Insp.OK</i>	<i>NoK</i>
VGG16_1	20.06	20.01	80	39.89	39.98	40
VGG16_2	60	60	40	48.99	48.99	48.99
VGG16_3	71.76	68.11	65.53	15.35	17.34	32.95
VGG16_4	70.89	69.22	73.19	9.56	11.82	6.54
VGG16_5	71.94	71.64	74.04	8.36	10.4	7.04
VGG16_6	67.22	67.77	76.6	9.32	10.81	9.13
VGG16_7	69.55	69.38	77.87	4.84	5.85	5.65
VGG16_8	79.04	79.16	59.57	11.94	12.41	31.59
VGG16_9	82.02	81.39	61.28	3.9	3.61	8.86
VGG16_10	66.78	65.54	78.72	8.03	8.42	12.41
VGG16_11	72.1	71.14	77.02	5.76	5.86	7.89

Although the best model was VGG16_7, it should be noted that, depending on the set of images that randomly configured the training set, the network learned or not, that is, the method was not robust enough.

4 Human Influence

Since the quality criteria is decided by human operators, a potentially relevant factor is the human bias or the multi-criteria developed by the different operators. To clarify such an effect, a heuristic feature extraction based on saliency map technology [12] was implemented where a Gaussian function was placed over every single defective pixel (see 4). After integrate all the damage functions contours can be derived.

Fig. 4: Digital representation of the defaults exhibited.

For each coil, defects over 40,25 and 10 levels of damage are obtained and the total area and number of clusters for each of the levels. In Fig. 5 there is no clear segmentation between OK and NoK, neither by the extension of the damaged area nor by the number of clusters. This analysis shows that the operator decision is not fully consistent as they do not produce a separated area

between the OK and NoK coils. Therefore, either more congruence is needed the operators' criteria or additional characteristics need to be considered for making a robust decision system more congruent with the adopted decisions. As a side effect, to keep the labeling as indicated in Fig.5, evidences the main reason why regardless of the DL technology being adopted, there is an upper bound to the accuracy reached.

Fig. 5: Synthetic feature map of coils.

5 Conclusions

This application shows how digitalization technology can help solve complex intrinsic problems by significantly improving success rates. Both deep learning and deep transfer learning have been tested to identify the quality of the provided solution, where ten runs have been elaborated to identify intrinsic variability due to the method itself. Obviously, there is a limit in the separation capabilities (about 70%), where additional effort is required to clarify the impact of the operators. Another reason to suppose such external influences is the significant behavior found during the sub-sampling instead of the Smote strategy. The reason why learning behavior increases with a lower number of randomly selected samples is that increasing the training set introduces a higher level of noise. Different strategies need to be decided in order to assess different criteria from the human operators, or additional factors need to be considered. To this end, we developed a dynamic workflow enabling the reassessment of synthetic maps, with shape rotation and different coil resequences. In this way, the impact of the human operator can be independently assessed. More work needs to be done in the coming weeks to allow a better assessment of human-based quality decisions.

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